

Sorption-Desorption Behaviour of the Amino Acids Glycine and Serine on Chemically Pretreated Silica Gel in Relation to Chromatography†

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Chemically pretreated (NaOH, KOH) silica gel samples of surface phase pH 7.0–11.0 were prepared and parameters like surface area, Na and K ion-content and H⁺ ion-exchange capacity determined. The samples were employed for the sorption-desorption study of the amino acids glycine and serine from 90% ethanol solutions. The sorption was found to depend on pH of the substrate and the alkali used for the pretreatment. The process was fast and almost athermic. Desorption efficacy and retarding influence on adsorption by electrolytes was in the order: Th(NO₃)₄ > Al(NO₃)₃ > Mg(NO₃)₂ > NaNO₃. The distribution coefficients for adsorption and desorption were employed in their column chromatography.

THE significance of pH in the adsorption of amino acids has been recognised¹. However, the use of chemically pretreated silica gel in these studies appears not to have received much attention. Earlier studies² on adsorption of amino acids on alumina and certain other adsorbents have shown them to be active adsorbents. The cation-exchange adsorption of some amino acids on Na, Mg, Cs, Co, Ni and Cu-forms of montmorillonite was studied by Tarasevich *et al.*³. The exchange behaviour of glutamic acid and glycine on cation-exchange resins has been studied⁴. In earlier studies⁵, the role of acid and alkali pretreatment of alumina on the adsorption of amino acids has been shown.

Silica is the most-widely used chromatographic adsorbent, and it has been shown⁶ that in water it has a negative charge, thought to be due to the ionisation of acidic hydroxyl groups,

Thus, silica gel exhibits cation-exchange character almost exclusively, and its isoelectric point is at pH ≈ 2.0. The weakly acidic (pH 3–5) surface of silica has a tendency towards preferential adsorption of strongly basic sample (pK_b < 5) relative to the adsorption on neutral or basic adsorbents (like alumina). However, O'Connor and Buchanan⁶ suggested that inorganic and organic anions are adsorbed by physical attraction, while the accompanying cations are adsorbed by ion-exchange. Haldemann and Emmett⁷, however, were able to prepare some special silica gels which adsorbed anionic solutes.

In spite of the excellent sorption characteristics, pretreatment of silica gel with various reagents to improve its sorption behaviour for specific type of sorbates, have been reported by various workers⁸. However, systematic attempt has possibly not been made to study the role of pH in the adsorption and desorption of the amino acids like glycine and serine on and from silica gel, pretreated with caustic alkalies (NaOH and KOH).

The present study deals with the following aspects: (i) extent of the influence of NaOH and KOH treatment of silica gel on its surface groups, (ii) role of specifically present cation (Na⁺ or K⁺) on the sorption behaviour of the neutral amino acids and (iii) desorption behaviour of the amino acids with solutions of inorganic electrolytes. As silica gel has no affinity for the amino acids in water, and since they are sparingly soluble in ethanol, the studies were carried out in 90% ethanol as a solvent.

Experimental

NaOH/KOH-treated silica gel samples (to be designated as SiO₂(s) and SiO₂(p), respectively) of pH 7.0–11.0 were prepared by treating (24 h, 25°) silica gel for column chromatography (B.D.H., pH 6.5) with varying concentrations of NaOH/KOH (0.005 to 1.0 N, 50 cm³), as described previously for alumina⁵.

The surface area of some of the samples was determined by the continuous flow method. H⁺-ion exchange capacity of the samples was determined by

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TABLE 1—CATION CONTENT, H⁺-ION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY AND SURFACE AREA OF ALKALI-TREATED SILICA GEL SAMPLES OF VARYING SURFACE-PHASE pH

Silica gel: Grain size=100–200 mesh. Surface area=245 m² g⁻¹. Pore size distribution=15–20 Å. H⁺-ion exchange capacity=0.16 meq/g. Na⁺ content=0.058 mg ion/g

Surface phase pH of silica gel*	Cation content mg ion g ⁻¹		H ⁺ -ion exchange capacity meq g ⁻¹		Surface area ±5 m ² g ⁻¹	
	Na ⁺	K ⁺	NaOH	KOH	NaOH	KOH
7.0	0.075	0.067	0.20	0.19	250	260
7.5	0.078	0.071	0.24	0.21	240	250
8.0	0.083	0.075	0.26	0.23	230	240
8.5	0.094	0.083	0.29	0.25	210	225
9.0	0.127	0.116	0.33	0.29	200	220
9.5	0.206	0.185	0.37	0.33	180	210
10.0	0.268	0.235	0.44	0.38	165	200
10.5	0.552	0.510	0.70	0.64	100	140
11.0	0.655	0.580	0.93	0.83	50	100

the pH-titration method. The cation (Na⁺ or K⁺) present on the alkali-treated samples was estimated⁹ (Table 1).

Glycine [Gly] (B.D.H.) and DL-serine [Ser] (E. Merck) were purified by crystallisation (thrice) from ethanol-water (1:1, v/v) and dried at 105°. A stock solution of the amino acid was prepared (2.00 mmol dm⁻³), and 5–80 cm³ of the solutions were withdrawn, diluted to 100 cm³, and the amino acid concentrations estimated colorimetrically at 570 nm using ninhydrin as the reagent¹⁰. The adsorption study on silica gel (0.10 g) was conducted with 90% ethanol solution (10 cm³) at different time intervals, temperatures and in presence of various inorganic electrolytes. The desorption study was conducted with 90% ethanol solutions of the same electrolytes. The other experimental details were the same as reported earlier⁵.

Results and Discussion

The variation of adsorption as a function of time (10 min–24 h, 30±1°, pH 7.0–11.0, 2.00–0.20 mmol dm⁻³) indicates fast adsorption in early stages. Thus, in 10 min, (2.00 mmol dm⁻³) glycine shows a maximum of 26% [SiO₂(s)] and 41% [SiO₂(p)] adsorption, while for serine the respective values are 63 and 58%. The equilibrium is attained in 6 h. The temperature effect studies (20–50°, 6 h, pH 7.0–11.0) are found to be almost athermic.

The results of sorption studies at different pH are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The phenomenon is found to be pH-dependant. Thus, adsorption on SiO₂(s) increases in the pH range 6.5–10.0 and the decrease occurs at pH >10.0. Glycine shows increasing adsorption on SiO₂(p) in the pH range 6.5–11.0. However, on SiO₂(p), the adsorption of serine increases in the pH range 6.5–9.0 followed by decrease at pH >9.0.

Adsorption studies in presence of electrolytes NaNO₃, Mg(NO₃)₂, Al(NO₃)₃ and Th(NO₃)₄ were carried out (30°, 24 h). The concentrations of the adsorbates and the electrolytes were the same, i.e.

Fig. 1. Change in the nature of adsorption of glycine from 90% ethanol solutions on alkali-treated silica gel of varying pH; time=24 h, temp.=30±1°.

2.00, 0.80 and 0.20 mmol dm⁻³. These conditions allow the electrolytes to compete for the adsorption sites on silica gel. The results (Fig. 3) reveal a significant decrease in adsorption (2.00 mmol dm⁻³). The electrolyte inhibiting effect follows the order: Th(NO₃)₄ > Al(NO₃)₃ > Mg(NO₃)₂ > NaNO₃.

Fig. 2. Change in the nature of adsorption of serine from 90% ethanol solutions on alkali-treated silica gel of varying pH; time=24 h, Temp.=30±1°.

Fig. 3. Percentage decrease in adsorption of neutral amino acids from 90% ethanol solutions in presence of electrolyte with varying pH of silica gel; time=24 h, Temp.=30±1°; [Amino acid]₀=[Electrolyte]₀=2.00 mmol dm⁻³.

Fig. 4. Percentage desorption of neutral amino acids adsorbed on silica gel of varying pH from 90% ethanol solutions by electrolyte solution (Time=24 h, Temp.=30±1°); [Amino acid]₀=2.00 mmol dm⁻³, [Electrolyte]₀=0.01 mol dm⁻³.

Desorption of the amino acids adsorbed on silica gel (pH 7.0–11.0, 30°, 24 h) was examined with the

inorganic electrolytes in 90% ethanol (0.001 and 0.01 *M*) as a function of pH of the substrates and concentrations of the amino acids (2.00, 0.80 and 0.20 mmol dm⁻³). The results (2.00 mmol dm⁻³ and electrolyte concentration 0.01 *M*) (Fig. 4) indicate the reversible nature of adsorption. Extractability of the amino acids adsorbed on silica gel depends upon pH of the substrates, the alkali used for pretreatment, the concentration and the nature of the amino acids. Thus, for the amino acids, the percentage-desorption first decreases with increasing pH (pH 8.0–10.0 [SiO₂(s)] and pH 8.0–9.0 [SiO₂(p)]) and then it increases upto pH 11.0. Thus, the amino acids show minimum desorption at pH 10.0 [SiO₂(s)] and pH 9.0 [SiO₂(p)]. Further, desorption of glycine is in the order : SiO₂(s) > SiO₂(p), while a reverse trend is observed in case of serine.

From the adsorption and desorption studies (batch operation), the distribution coefficients for adsorption (*K_a* cm³ g⁻¹) and desorption (*K_D* g cm⁻³) were also calculated⁵. On the basis of these data, the elution studies were performed with 90% ethanol solution (0.01 *M*) of the electrolytes. Glass column (10×0.5 cm) was dry-packed with silica gel (1.0 g) and the exchanger was kept in contact with ethanol solution of the amino acid (0.80 mmol dm⁻³, 2 h). The column was then washed with the desired eluent (1 cm³ min⁻¹) and the effluent solutions (2 cm³) collected and analysed. The volume of the eluate was plotted against concentration of the amino acid (percentage elution) to obtain the elution curves. The retention volume (*V_R*) and the total volume of the eluent required for complete elution (*V_T*) were computed from the elution curves. A few results are shown in Table 2. On the basis of the chromatographic parameters, the two amino acids, from their synthetic mixtures, were separated in the glass column. The characteristics of the separation are shown in Table 2.

The adsorption of polar organic solutes can be influenced in a number of ways. The weak protic solutes may undergo speciation with pH. The oxide

surface which shows acid-base characteristics can be affected with pH. This results in charged-groups as shown in equation (2). Such groups exert differing preferences for organic solutes¹¹.

Surface at high pH

Surface at low pH

Treatment of silica gel with alkali (MOH) may cover the surface with alkali cations as

The cations on the surface may be easily exchanged by the in-going cations, since Na⁺/K⁺ ions are much lower than H⁺-ion in the ion selectivity series of hydrous oxides. Further, the number of exchangeable Na⁺/K⁺ ions present on the surface increases with increasing surface-phase pH of silica gel (Table 1).

The apparent dissociation constants (25°) of the amino acids are¹² : glycine p*K*₁, 2.34 ; p*K*₂ (NH₄⁺), 9.60 ; p*I*, 5.97 ; and serine p*K*₁, 2.21 ; p*K*₂ (NH₄⁺), 9.15 ; p*I*, 5.68. So, in aqueous solution, zwitterionic form of the amino acids predominates. In the alkaline pH range (> 7.0), the anionic form is the principal species in solution. On the other hand, silica is known to act as a cation-exchanger at pH ≥ 2.0. Because of the two opposing effects of pH on the substrate as well as the solutes in aqueous medium, adsorption affinity is absent. In 90% ethanol medium, the amino acids carry a negative charge on account of the lowering of isoelectric pH from the original value (pH ≈ 6.0)¹. Hence, the chance of adsorption of the amino acids by ion-exchange does not appear to be feasible in this medium also. However, the amino acids show considerable adsorption on silica gel in the pH range 6.5–11.0.

Morrison¹³ observed adsorption of negatively charged species onto oxides at pH above the i.e.p. in the case of α-hydroxy acids. It was explained

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF GLYCINE AND SERINE ON ALKALI-TREATED SILICA GEL

Spen. no.	pH of silica gel/and column height, cm)	Amino acid	Distribution coefficient		Electrolyte solution (0.01 <i>M</i>) used as eluent	Elution parameters ^a (cm ³ g ⁻¹)		Volume required cm ³	Recovery %
			for adsorption (cm ³ g ⁻¹) × 10 ⁻³	for desorption (g cm ⁻³) × 10 ³		<i>V_R</i>	<i>V_T</i>		
NaOH-treated silica gel									
1a.	9.0 (6)	Gly	0.10	16.54	Th(NO ₃) ₄	4	6	15	99.5
		Ser	0.60	3.55	Th(NO ₃) ₄	11	15	25	99.0
1b.	8.0 (8)	Gly	0.06	3.95	Al(NO ₃) ₃	8	14	24	99.3
		Ser	0.52	1.22	Th(NO ₃) ₄	22	34	40	99.0
KOH-treated silica gel									
2a.	9.0 (6)	Gly	0.10	11.50	Th(NO ₃) ₄	6	12	20	99.6
		Ser	0.70	1.45	Th(NO ₃) ₄	26	40	50	99.0
2b.	8.0 (8)	Gly	0.07	3.20	Mg(NO ₃) ₂	10	16	30	99.2
		Ser	0.59	0.75	Th(NO ₃) ₄	32	46	60	99.0

^aValues are for the first eluent used in the separation.

in terms of hydrogen bonding between α -hydroxyl groups of the acid and the negatively charged oxide ions on the surface. A similar mechanism was assumed for the adsorption of α -amino acids on amorphous hydrous titanium(IV) oxide, where electrostatic repulsion prevails¹⁴. So, it is likely that the forces operating in this process are predominantly hydrogen bonds or dipole-dipole interactions, as

for serine. This is also indicated by the moderately fast nature of adsorption and its almost athermic nature.

The characteristic feature of this study is retardation of adsorption in presence of electrolytes in the adsorption bath (Fig. 3) and significant desorption of the adsorbed species by the electrolytes (Fig. 4). These suggest that electrostatic forces (ion-exchange) may be responsible for the process. However, this possibility does not appear to be feasible (as explained earlier). The role of electrolytes may be interpreted in terms of weakening of H-bonds by the cations in the adsorption bath. S-type isotherms (Figs. 1 and 2) indicate cooperative adsorption.

Thus, chemical pretreatment of silica gel with alkali appears to enhance the adsorption affinity of the sorbent. This may be due to hydrogen bonding and dipole-dipole interaction. The chromatographic separation of the amino acids demonstrates the analytical application of pretreated silica gel.

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